

THE USE OF RADIFS IN ERKIN VAHIDOV'S LYRICS

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Abstract. In this article, one of the powerful poets of the 20th century, writer Erkin Vahidov, who has his own place in the world of poetry, researches the radifs used in "Devon of Youth". The statistics of the radifs used in the poet's lyrics were made, and certain conclusions were made regarding the purpose of use and their importance in enhancing the meaning. For several ghazals, attention is focused on the same bases taken as a radif, and the commonalities and differences in them are shown.

Keywords: radif, one-word radif, two-word radif, three-word radif, yiqiq radif, yoyik radif, ilmi aruz, ilmi bade', ilmi kafiya, artistic, ramal, narrator, rhymer, finger weight, modern poetry, talmih, tazad, proverb, phrase.

It is known that the classical poetry of the Ancient East was built on three sciences. These include "ilmi bade'", "ilmi aruz" and "ilmi qafiya". It was considered necessary for every poet to know these three sciences. Because only with the support of these sciences, unique works of art, poetic arts, and perfect weight and rhyme were created. Without them, the poet's talent remained incomplete. Both in the early and later periods of classical literature, these three were observed equally. We can see proof of this in the works of Lutfiy, Navoi, Fuzuli, Muqimi, Zavqi, Furqat, Ogahii, as well as in the poetry of Abdulla Oripov and Erkin Vahidov. In "Ilmi bade'", the rules of the weight of aruz in "ilmi aruz" are the correct use of each poetic art, be it verbal or spiritual, in its place. which genre should be written in what weight, zihof, wasl phenomena, types, elements and radif of rhyme are taught in the

"science of rhyme". Taking into account the importance of these sciences, we found it necessary to study the use of radif in the example of Erkin Vahidov's "Department of Youth".

By the 20th century, the finger weight became popular in Uzbek poetry, and it is no exaggeration to say that the creators used this weight and took it to a higher level. But there is another side of the coin, which is the heart of Turkish poetry over the centuries. Seeing it as a "sign of old age", the creators of the era did not write a verse in this weight. At such a time, modern poets such as Abdulla Oripov and Erkin Vahidov did not abandon the dream. In particular, Erkin Vahidov collected the works he finished in Aruz weight and created "Devon of Youth". Each stanza of Devon can prove how well the poet knew the science of rhyme, poetic arts and aruz. Our famous poet, academician Gafur Ghulam expressed the following opinion about the poet's poetry: "In free poetry, he jumped past the period of imitation. He did not imitate Navoi, Babur, or Mashrab. He did not become a prisoner of them. He learned the secrets of poetry of those classical poets. Even when he learned, he learned again and again. In fact, we can imagine how much great talent and knowledge the poet has, on the example of Erkin Vahidov's skill of using radif.

Radif is a word that means "following" and in literary studies it means a word or combination of words that comes after a rhyme and repeats itself.[2,156] Poets can have several purposes for using radif. Erkin Vahidov also made good use of radifs. In particular, during our calculations, we witnessed that radif was used in 70% of the poet's literary heritage of more than 500 stanzas collected in "Youth Cabinet". If we take into account that radifs are divided into types such as radifs, one-word, two-word, three-word, multi-word radifs, only one-word radifs were used in the poet's work. If some words are radif only once, i.e. in one ghazal, it is possible to find several ghazals with the same radif in the divan.

*May all the joy be yours, my dear, the hardships are mine,
All the pleasure is for you, and all the pleasure is for me.[1,62]*

There are probably few poetry lovers who do not know the above verse. The word "menga" is used as a radif in the ghazal that begins with this verse, which is raised to the level of Shahbayt. In our classic literature, we can see that the word "menga" is translated into "manga", "mango" in the lyrics of many artists such as Navoi, Mashrab, Ogahi. And for Erkin Vahidov, this has a more special meaning. From the beginning to the end of the ghazal, the repetition of the phrase "menga" next to words such as "illness, hummorlik, thorniness, dilafgorlik", used to show the tolerance characteristic of lovers.

We turn to the next stanza:

*Don't despise when you're lying down, who's actually watching
That's it, my dear, don't rub it in your eyes.[1,64]*

In this stanza, the word "surma" is strongly emphasized, and the poet sometimes describes it, sometimes qualifies it, and sometimes directly addresses it. Through the appeal, we can also understand that the lyrical hero is envious of the antimony that landed in his eyes. Because the diamond is in the eyes of the beloved, that is, close to her. Next stanza:

*Don't put any blame on the heart of love,
If there is a bandi, it is a fisherman, and if there is no food, it is a
fault.[1,69]*

"Ayb" radiative ghazal not only reflects the traditions of classical literature, but also features typical of modern literature. In the ghazal, the poet sometimes puts the "guilt" on someone or something, and sometimes exonerates the sinner. In our opinion, the author used the word "blame" as a radiative to achieve his artistic and aesthetic goal. Because from time immemorial important words have been given as radif. We can also see the situation of "imposing responsibility" on Radif in the next ghazal:

*He who has no talent loses his skill with knowledge.
Don't worry about giving talent, it will be wasted.[1,74]*

We tentatively call the ghazal "Zoye" radifli ghazal. The main idea in this ghazal is clarified by the use of the word taken from the radif. In particular, the poet tried to convey to the reader the idea that it is useless to teach science and craft to a person without talent, to give gold and gems to a weak-hearted person, to make the sun shine on a cold-hearted person, and to give a purple and gold belt to a hare-brained person by repeating the word "zoye", and he succeeded in this. The poet's ghazal "No" is considered very artistically perfect. Although the radif word is unintentionally reminiscent of Alisher Navoi's radif ghazal "No", Erkin Vahidov's ghazal is quite different from that of the sultan of nazm property. We can also notice this from the matla:

There is no threshold where I did not hit my stone head,

There is such a proverb: If you don't smoke, you don't have a soul.[1,110]

It is no exaggeration to say that the author proved that he is a connoisseur of folk proverbs and expressions with these two verses. Because the phrase "I have a stone head" in the first verse reminds us of the saying of our people "Let your head be made of stone", and the proverb in the second verse - "If you don't smoke, you don't have a soul" is the basis of the art of proverbs. The tone and meaning of the ghazal is also very playful, poetic arts such as talmih (Qays), tazad (insanity), tanosub (mast, may, maykhana) and nido (white paper) used in the following verses can prove this.

Erkin Vahidov also wrote several ghazals with the same rhythm. The reason for this can be explained by the fact that only this radif repetition is suitable for the content of the ghazal, or that the poet's artistic goal in using the word taken from the radif was not sufficiently realized in one ghazal. For example, in "Devon of Youth" we come across two ghazals with the radix "kalam". The author named these two as "Kalam" and "Yana kalamga" and it will not be a mistake if we say that thoughts that have not been fully expressed in one ghazal will be transferred to the

next ghazal, so to speak, it will be the basis. Let me bring to your attention the matla of both ghazals:

*It's my honor, the candle light, the solitary pen of the nights,
I am the Majnuni of poetry, the pen of Sarvkad Laila. [1,84]*

*Let my leaf and flower paper die, the branch is a flower and a pen.
Let the words of the nightingale come together, the words of love, the
essay, the pen. [1,88]*

Since both ghazals are written in the same mahzaf weight, and the rhyme is similar, that is, the narrator's sound is the letter "o" in both ghazals, it seems difficult to distinguish them from each other at first glance. They are similar in terms of idea and content. Because in the 1st ghazal, the poet calls himself Majnun and the pen as Laila, in the next ghazal, he considers this object to be a pain in the ass and creates beautiful descriptions using similes. If we look for ghazals with the same rhythm from Devon, two ghazals entitled "Davron Yuki" and "Hijran Yuki" will definitely attract our attention. In fact, these ghazals have the same weight, the same narrator, and naturally the same radif and tone as the above radifs.

Matla of "The Burden of Time":

*The burden of a thousand centuries of heaven from the head of a spinning man,
A grain of wheat is like the weight of a mill.[1,76]*

Matla of "Hijran Burden":

*The sudden burden of hijra on the heart until I agree,
Suddenly, let the burden of my soul be removed from my body.[1,79]*

It is also known from Matla's that two ghazals are close to each other in terms of form, but very far in terms of content. In other words, we should not lose sight of the meaning while listening to the tone. The first ghazal reflects social issues, thoughts about the world and man, and didactic ideas, while the epigraph of Alisher

Navoi's verse "Aylagin jondin judo, etgancha jondondin judo" by Alisher Navoi is used as an epigraph, and the main theme is to show the sufferings of a lover.

In the works of Erkin Vahidov, we can see the case where auxiliary words are also used as adverbs. For example, two ghazals with the radix "Ham" and two ghazals with the radix "Bilan" are included in "Youth Divan". We can see similarities in form, weight and rhyme in the radiative ghazals of "Bilan". In one of them, the words tarozu, inju, jodu, gulgu, kuzgu, and dream are the basis of the rhyme, while in the other words such as yogdu, water, ogu, sadness, and sleep are rhymed. Both ghazals are romantic ghazals. In contrast to the above, it is difficult to notice the formal similarity in ghazals with the "Ham" radix. The reason for this can be explained by the fact that the narrators in the rhyme are not the same. But both ghazals are known and popular among fans of literature. One of them was named by the poet "Dost il obod yunyin" and the second one was called "Rashkim". If we pay attention to matlas:

*"Make a good home with a friend, even if it is a ruin,
If a friend does not take a step, the house is ruined. [1,86]*

*"I will even make you jealous even of myself,
If I stay longer, I will be out of sight." [1,87]*

So we can say that the similarity in the radif is just a random similarity. In addition, Erkin Vahidov effectively used radifs with the same base. That is, in the work of the poet, we can find ghazals with the radix "do, do, don't, do" related to the verb "do". These ghazals are close to each other in content. The ghazals with "Qilsin", "Qilmas" and "Qilur" radix are on a romantic theme, but the ghazal with the radix "Qil" is taken from the poet's "Kulgu Mushoiralari" series. The author himself named the ghazal "Admonition" and a comic spirit is felt in it. We can also notice this from Matla:

Do not make the hand skilled in work, make the tongue master in speech,

When you do something, do it right.[1,113]

The poet did not deviate from formal and spiritual perfection even in his comic poems.

To sum up, Erkin Vahidov, as a connoisseur of the "science of rhyme", was able to use radifs in their proper place, in a variety of ways. None of Radif's post-rhyme repetitions are superfluous, superficial. On the contrary, in each repetition of the word taken from the radif, one can feel different aspects of meaning, a different emphasis and a different tone. Perhaps because of this, the poet's literary heritage does not lose its longevity even though the times change, it keeps finding new admirers and conquering the hearts of fans of poetry.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. E. Vahidov. Selected works. - Tashkent: Sharq, 2018.
2. A. Hojiahmedov. Poetic arts and classical rhyme. - Tashkent: Sharq, 1998.
3. A. Hosseini. Badoye us-sano'ye. -Tashkent: Gafur Ghulam, 1981.
4. Hamdam Abdullayev. Erkin Vahidov is a classic of our time. -Tashkent: 2006.
5. T. Boboyev. Poetry education. -Tashkent: "Teacher", 1996.
6. T. Boboyev. Basics of literary studies. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2002.